

Synthesis of some Bimetallic Trinuclear Ru^{II}–Ni^{II}–Ru^{II} Complexes

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Reactions of $[\text{Ni}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{L}_2]^{2+}$ {L = 4-cyanopyridine, 1,4-dicyanobenzene, 1,4-dicyanopiperazine, 1,4-dicyano-*trans*-2-butene (referred hereafter as CNPy, DCB, PPz and DCBT respectively) with $[\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{ClE}_2]$ {E₂ = (PPh₃)₂, (AsPh₃)₂, Sb(Ph₃)₂ and dppm) have been carried out in presence of suitable anions like BF₄⁻, BPh₄⁻, PF₆⁻ and ClO₄⁻, to obtain cationic bimetallic trinuclear complexes of the type $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{-Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-Ru}^{\text{II}}]^{2+}$. The reaction products have been characterised by elemental analyses and ir, electronic, ¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P nmr spectral studies.

There has been a growing interest in the investigation of homo- and heteropolynuclear complexes largely stimulated by (i) their importance in the possible catalytic activity enhancement with respect to their corresponding monomeric analogues¹, (ii) the possibility of covalently linked chromophore-luminophore complex synthesis for the solar energy utilisation² and (iii) the exchange coupled polynuclear synthesis³. The literature survey indicated a rather large number of bimetallic dinuclear complexes and only a few heterometallic trinuclear ones^{2,4-7}. As an extension of our interest in the synthesis of polynuclear complexes⁸⁻¹² using organonitriles like 4-cyanopyridine (CNPy), 1,4-dicyanobenzene (DCB), 1,4-piperazine dicarbonitrile (PPz) and 1,4-*trans*-dicyanobutene (DCBT) as bridging ligands, an initial attempt is made to synthesise the heterotrinuclear complexes of Ru^{II} and Ni^{II} using $[\text{Ru}(\text{Cp})\text{E}_2\text{X}]$ {E₂ = (PPh₃)₂, (AsPh₃)₂, (SbPh₃)₂, dppm; X = Cl} and $[\text{Ni}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{L}_2]^{2+}$ (L = CNPy, DCB, DCBT, PPz) as starting materials. These bridging systems are of interest in various fields, for example, in understanding the biological

redox process-mechanism. An additional feature of this study was to investigate the effect of bonding properties of the second functional group remote from the coordinated site in the mononuclear complexes. The present communication is a preliminary report in this direction.

Results and Discussion

Reaction between $[\text{Ni}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{L}_2]^{2+}$, where {L₂ = 4-cyanopyridine, 4-dicyanobenzene, 1,4-dicyanopiperazine and 1,4-dicyano-2-butene} and $[\text{Re}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{E}_2\text{Cl}]$, where {E₂ = (PPh₃)₂, (AsPh₃)₂, (SbPh₃)₂, dppe and dppm} yields yellow to orange brown non-hygroscopic air-stable microcrystalline complexes. Their melting points are in the range of 125–165° and a few complexes decomposed without melting. Most of the complexes are soluble in common organic solvents like benzene, dichloromethane, acetonitrile, dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulphoxide, and insoluble in alcohol, petroleum ether, diethyl ether and methanol. Analytical and spectral data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, IR AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA

Sl. no.	Compd./ (colour, m.p. °C)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ν _{C=N}	Nmr data (δ)		
		C	H	N		¹ H	¹³ C	³¹ P
1.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₆ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)P ₂ }] ₂ (BF ₄) ₄ (Orange yellow, 167)	61.83 (61.54)	4.57 (4.41)	1.24 (1.15)	2 230	4.8, 7.2–7.8, 8.25, 9.1	81.5, 117	7.5, 32
2.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₆ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)P ₂ }] ₂ (PF ₆) ₄ (Orange yellow, 139)	56.54 (56.15)	4.21 (4.02)	1.14 (1.05)	2 232	4.8, 7.2–7.8, 8.2, 9.2	140–145, 127–132	

(Table-1 (Contd.))

3.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{P}_2\}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (Orange yellow, 146)	60.89 (60.29)	4.56 (4.32)	1.42 (1.13)	2 225	4.8, 7.2-7.8, 8.1, 9.2	
4.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{dppf})_2\}](\text{BF}_4)_4$ (Orange yellow, 157)	57.96 (57.63)	4.84 (4.37)	1.29 (1.29)	2 230	4.8, 7.2-7.8, 8.2, 9.1	
5.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{dppf})_2\}](\text{PF}_6)_4$ (Orange yellow, 169)	52.07 (52.04)	4.17 (3.99)	1.26 (1.16)	2 230	4.8, 7.2-7.8, 8.2, 9.2	
6.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{dppf})_2\}](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (Orange yellow, 134)	56.42 (56.30)	4.37 (4.27)	1.25 (1.26)	2 235	4.8, 7.2-7.8, 8.2, 9.1	
7.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{A})_2\}](\text{BF}_4)_4$ (Orange yellow, 156)	58.12 (57.38)	4.32 (4.11)	1.36 (1.07)	2 230	4.8, 7.2-7.8, 8.2, 9.2	81.4, 177, 140-145, 127-128
8.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{A})_2\}](\text{PF}_6)_4$ (Light yellow, 163)	52.92 (52.66)	3.80 (3.77)	34 (0.99)	2 225	4.7, 7.2-7.9, 8.2, 9.2	
10.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{A})_2\}](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (Orange yellow, 156)	56.92 (56.28)	4.21 (4.03)	1.33 (1.05)	2 230	4.8, 7.2-7.9, 8.2, 9.2	
11.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{Sb})_2\}](\text{BF}_4)_4$ (Orange, 129)	53.64 (53.51)	3.92 (3.83)	1.14 (1.00)	2 230	4.8, 7.2-7.8, 8.1, 9.2	
12.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{Sb})_2\}](\text{PF}_6)_4$ (Orange, 134)	44.40 (44.38)	3.40 (3.54)	1.12 (0.92)	2 230	4.7, 7.2-7.8, 8.2, 9.2	
13.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{Sb})_2\}](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (Orange)	52.32	6.36	1.20	2 228	4.7, 7.2-7.8, 8.2, 9.1	
14.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{P}_2\}_2](\text{BF}_4)_4$ (Pale yellow, 145)	62.12 (61.60)	4.67 (4.33)	1.40 (1.58)	2 260	4.5, 7.2-7.9, 3.2, 5.8	
15.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{P}_2\}_2](\text{PF}_6)_4$ (Pale yellow, 149)	56.26 (56.19)	4.24 (3.95)	1.62 (1.05)	2 265	4.5, 7.2-7.8, 3.2, 5.8	
16.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{P}_2\}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (Pale yellow, 157)	61.21 (60.34)	4.54 (4.24)	1.16 (1.13)	2 260	4.5, 7.2-7.8, 3.2, 5.8	
17.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{dppf})_2\}](\text{BF}_4)_4$ (Pale yellow, 147)	58.22 (57.68)	4.31 (4.28)	1.50 (1.29)	2 265	4.5, 7.2-7.8, 3.2, 5.8	
18.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{dppf})_2\}](\text{PF}_6)_4$ (Pale yellow, 153)	52.32 (52.08)	3.91 (3.86)	1.36 (1.16)	2 265	4.5, 7.2-7.8, 3.2, 5.6	
19.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{dppf})_2\}](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (Pale yellow, 151)	56.20 (56.20)	4.67 (4.18)	1.34 (1.26)	2 260	4.5, 7.2-7.9, 3.2, 5.7	
20.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{A})_2\}_2](\text{BF}_4)_4$ (Pale yellow, 159)	57.53 (57.42)	4.31 (4.04)	1.22 (1.08)	2 265	4.5, 7.2-7.9, 3.2	
21.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{A})_2\}_2](\text{PF}_6)_4$ (Pale yellow, 167)	52.90 (52.69)	3.91 (3.70)	1.40 (0.99)	2 262	4.5, 7.2-7.9, 3.2	
22.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{A})_2\}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (Light yellow, 160)	56.80 (56.32)	4.21 (3.96)	1.36 (1.05)	2 265	4.5, 7.2-7.9, 3.2	
23.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{A})_2\}_2](\text{BF}_4)_4$ (Light yellow, 163)	43.67 (43.55)	3.84 (3.76)	1.23 (1.00)	2 260	4.5, 7.2-7.8, 3.2, 5.8	
24.	$[\text{P}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)\{\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{A})_2\}_2](\text{PF}_6)_4$ (Light yellow, 149)	57.46 (57.68)	6.20 (6.15)	1.12 (0.92)	2 265	4.6, 7.2-7.8, 3.2, 5.8	

(Table-1 (Contd.))

25.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(A) ₂ }] ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄ (Light yellow, 139)	52.81 (52.60)	4.23 (3.70)	1.42 (0.98)	2 265	4.6, 7.2-7.8	
26.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)P ₂ }] ₂ (BF ₄) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 167)	62.35 (61.97)	4.62 (4.29)	1.51 (1.14)	2 225	4.6, 7.2-7.8	84.56, 119.9
27.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)P ₂ }] ₂ (PF ₆) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 160)	56.93 (56.58)	4.26 (3.91)	1.32 (1.04)	2 228	4.56, 7.2-7.8	84.58, 120
28.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)P ₂ }] ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 159)	61.29 (60.72)	4.31 (4.20)	1.22 (1.12)	2 230	4.6, 7.2-7.8	84.59, 119.5
29.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(dppe)} ₂](BF ₄) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 164)	58.21 (58.14)	4.34 (4.28)	1.27 (1.27)	2 225	4.6, 7.2-7.8	84.5, 119.4
30.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(dppe)} ₂](PF ₆) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 163)	52.82 (52.56)	3.91 (3.82)	1.52 (1.15)	2 225	4.55, 7.2-7.8	84.45, 119.7
31.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(dppe)} ₂](ClO ₄) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 169)	57.94 (57.82)	4.56 (4.13)	1.40 (1.25)	2 222	4.57, 7.2-7.8	84.6, 119.5
32.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(A) ₂ }] ₂ (BF ₄) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 173)	58.26 (57.81)	4.23 (4.00)	1.30 (1.07)	2 225	4.59, 7.2-7.8	84.65, 119.6
33.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(A) ₂ }] ₂ (PF ₆) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 143)	53.13 (53.09)	3.91 (3.67)	1.20 (0.98)	2.228	4.6, 7.2-7.8	84.55, 119.67
34.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(A) ₂ }] ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 159)	57.19 (56.71)	4.12 (3.92)	1.16 (0.95)	2 230	4.6, 7.2-7.8	84.56, 119.8
35.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(Sb) ₂ }] ₂ (PF ₆) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 157)	45.35 (44.82)	3.64 (3.45)	1.43 (0.92)	2 225	4.58, 7.2-7.8	84.57, 120
36.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(Sb) ₂ }] ₂ (BF ₄) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 154)	54.26 (53.95)	3.81 (3.73)	1.26 (0.99)	2 225	4.6, 7.2-7.8	84.6, 119.2
37.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₈ H ₄ N ₂){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(Sb) ₂ }] ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄ (Yellow-orange, 159)	53.20 (52.99)	3.91 (3.67)	1.42 (0.98)	2 225	4.58, 7.2-7.8	84.56, 1120
38.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₈ N ₄){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)P ₂ }] ₂ (BF ₄) ₄ (Light brown, 149)	61.23 (60.79)	4.34 (4.44)	1.30 (2.28)	2 225, 2 265		
39.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₈ N ₄){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)P ₂ }] ₂ (PF ₆) ₄ (Light brown, 152)	56.39 (55.72)	4.27 (4.07)	2.30 (2.09)	2 225, 2 265		
40.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₈ N ₄){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)P ₂ }] ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄ (Light brown, 148)	60.11 (59.56)	4.67 (4.35)	2.40 (2.24)	2 220, 2 265		
41.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₈ N ₄){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(dppe)} ₂](BF ₄) ₄ (Light brown, 191)	57.20 (56.84)	4.53 (4.40)	2.91 (2.54)	2 225, 2 260		
42.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₈ N ₄){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(dppe)} ₂](PF ₆) ₄ (Light brown, 139)	52.46 (51.40)	4.16 (3.98)	2.34 (2.30)	2 225, 2 265		
43.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₈ N ₄){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(dppe)} ₂](ClO ₄) ₄ (Light brown, 147)	58.61 (58.13)	4.62 (4.50)	2.72 (2.60)	2 220, 2 260		
44.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₈ N ₄){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(A) ₂ }] ₂ (BF ₄) ₄ (Light brown, 163)	56.74 (56.72)	4.26 (4.14)	2.37 (2.19)	2 220, 2 260		
45.	[P ₂ Ni(μ-C ₆ H ₈ N ₄){Ru(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)(A) ₂ }] ₂ (PF ₆) ₄ (Light brown, 163)	52.61 (52.10)	3.90 (3.80)	2.31 (1.96)	2 220, 2 265		

46	$[P_2Ni(\mu-C_6H_8N_4)\{Ru(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(A)_2\}](ClO_4)_4$ (Light brown, 169)	55 94 (55 64)	4 32 (4 06)	2 17 (2 09)	2 225, 2 260
47	$[P_2Ni(\mu-C_6H_8N_4)\{Ru(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(A)_2\}](BF_4)_4$ (Light brown, 159)	53 12 (52 44)	3 96 (3 86)	2.12 (1.99)	2 225, 2 255
48	$[P_2Ni(\mu-C_6H_8N_4)\{Ru(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(A)_2\}](PF_6)_4$ (Light brown, 160)	49 14 (48.90)	3.82 (3 57)	1 96 (1 83)	2 220, 2 260
49	$[P_2Ni(\mu-C_6H_8N_4)\{Ru(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(Sb)_2\}](ClO_4)_4$ (Light brown, 163)	52.81 (52 01)	3.96 (3.80)	2.51 (1 95)	2 225, 2 265

* $P_2 = (PPh_3)_2$; $A_2 = (AsPh_3)_2$; $Sb_2 = (SbPh_3)_2$ and dppe = diphenylphosphinoethano

Ir spectra : For elucidation of the coordination sites in the complexes the shifts in the position of ν_{CN} has been used. On coordination through nitrogen, ν_{CN} of the nitrile group should shift to lower energy on coordination. Ir spectra of the 4-cyanopyridine complexes exhibited ν_{CN} as a broad band at $2\ 230\ cm^{-1}$. As expected the bands shifted towards lower wavenumbers in the reaction products. This shift in the position of ν_{CN} may be attributed to the metal-to-ligand π -backbonding. This is due to the drift of electron density from the d_π orbitals of the metal to the π^* orbital of the CN group. Broadness of the band indicates the presence of two 4-cyanopyridine molecules in the *cis*-position. The band at $1\ 450$ – $1\ 600\ cm^{-1}$ also indicates the presence of two pyridine rings^{21–24}. Characteristic bands of EPh_3 and anions present (BF_4^- , BPh_4^- , PF_6^- , ClO_4^-) were also present in the spectra. In the case of dicyanobenzene complexes, the ν_{CN} band is present at about $2\ 225\ cm^{-1}$ as an intense broad band. Here also a shift towards low wavenumber side is observed. This shift (from $2\ 232$ to $2\ 225\ cm^{-1}$) indicates the direct coordination of the N atom of the nitrile group with the metal centre (Ru). It may be due to the drift of electron density from metal d_π orbitals to the π^* orbitals of the CN group. Characteristic ir bands of EPh_3 and the anions present in the complexes were also observed in the complexes. A prominent feature of the ir spectrum of the 1,4-dicyano-*trans*-butene ligand is the presence of an intense and sharp band at $2\ 280\ cm^{-1}$ which has been assigned to ν_{CN} . The cationic complexes of 1,4-dicyano-*trans*-2-butene containing $Ni \begin{matrix} \nearrow Ru \\ \searrow Ru \end{matrix}$ exhibit a sharp single band in the nitrile region around $2\ 265\ cm^{-1}$,

assignable to ν_{CN} which exhibits a red-shift, suggesting the coordination with the metal centre. Broadness and splitting of this band indicates the presence of two dicyanobutene ligands in the complexes. The splitting of the band may arise due to the interaction between these two dicyanobutene molecules. The decrease in ν_{CN} stretching frequency may be attributed to the back-acceptance of electron density from Ru^{II} to π^* orbitals of the CN group in a linear metal nitrogen-carbon configuration. To explain the ir spectra of the piperazine complexes, it has been presumed that the ligand exists in the *N,N'*-disubstituted nitrile form ($\ddot{N}=C-N$). The possibility of its existence in carbodiimide form ($-N=C-N-$) is remote. It can only contribute as a resonating structure where the lone-pair of electrons on N-CN nitrogen participate in the delocalisation process ($>\ddot{N}=C-\ddot{N}:>$)^{26–28}. This too is possible when the electron is present in the pure p_z orbital. Thus one expects ir active bands due to $\nu_{C=N}$, ν_{C-N} and ν_{CN-CN} around $2\ 250$, $1\ 000$ and $400\ cm^{-1}$. The ir spectrum of piperazine exhibits bands at $2\ 240$, $1\ 010$ and $410\ cm^{-1}$, supporting the first model.

Ir spectra of the PPz complexes exhibit bands around $2\ 265$ (two), $1\ 010$ (two) and $450\ cm^{-1}$ (broad). The shift in the band at $2\ 240\ cm^{-1}$ towards higher wavenumber suggests direct coordination of nitrile nitrogen with Ru^{II} and also indicates the withdrawal of electron density from the CN group and thus enhancement in the CN bond order. Splitting was observed in the spectra of these complexes which indicates the presence of neighbour interaction²⁷. Thus it seems likely that two ligand molecules (piperazine) are bonded to the metal centres. Characteristic bands due to co-

ligands and the anions are also present in the ir spectra of the complexes.

¹H nmr spectra : The ¹H nmr spectra of the trinuclear bimetallic complexes of 4-cyanopyridine with PPh₃/AsPh₃ as co-ligands exhibit sharp signals at δ 4.8. The observed downfield shift of η⁵-C₅H₅ proton may be attributed to the change of electron density on ruthenium due to backbonding from metal to 4-cyanopyridine. This is further supported by the presence of strong electron-withdrawing group like -C≡N at the *para*-position. The electron-withdrawing and conjugative ability of -CN, withdraws electron density from the pyridine nucleus towards itself which results in the deshielding of electron on the ruthenium metal, and consequently pulls electron density from the (η⁵-C₅H₅) group. Broad signals at δ 7.8–9.1 and 9.1–9.3 have been assigned to 4-cyanopyridine protons^{19–29}. The presence of these signals supports the presence of 4-cyanopyridine in the complexes. Characteristic bands of EPh₃ (δ 7.2–7.8) were present in the complexes as broad multiplets.

In the trinuclear dicyanobenzene complexes, the η⁵-C₅H₅ protons resonate at δ 4.6. Here also a downfield shift is observed. These shifts are comparable to those of [Ru(η⁵-C₅H₅)(EPh₃)₂(CN)], suggesting that the CN moiety in dicyanobenzene affects the environment of η⁵-C₅H₅ protons in a way similar to CN. The phenyl protons of dicyanobenzene group resonate along with the EPh₃ protons at δ 7.2–7.8 as broad multiplets. ¹H nmr spectra of 1,4-dicyanobutene complexes exhibit a sharp single band at δ 4.5 assigned to η⁵-C₅H₅ protons in the case of PPh₃/AsPh₃ complexes. In Sb(Ph₃)₂ complexes, this band occurs around δ 4.7–4.9 ppm. The downfield shift and occurrence as split band may be due to interaction of η⁵-C₅H₅ protons with the bulky SbPh₃ groups slightly tilted in configuration. The aromatic protons appear as broad multiplets in the region δ 7.2–7.8. In the absence of any π-backbonding from Ru^{II} to dicyanobutene ligand in the complexes, inductive effects due to -C≡N group exhibit a multiplet at δ 3.2 as compared to δ 3.18 in the free ligand. The olefinic protons were found to be shifted in the complexes (ca δ 5.8) as compared to the free ligands (ca δ 5.83). ¹H nmr spectra of 1,4-piperazine dicarbonitrile complexes exhibit bands around δ 4.6, 7.2–7.7 (multiplet) and 3.1, which have been assigned to η⁵-C₅H₅ protons,

phenyl protons of EPh₃ group and CH₂ protons of piperazine ring.

¹³C nmr spectra : The ¹³C nmr spectra of the 4-cyanopyridine complexes show signals at δ 84.8, 120 and 128–134 ppm, which have been assigned to cyclopentadienyl carbon atoms, nitrile carbon atom of the 4-cyanopyridine group and to the phenyl carbon atoms respectively. Downfield shifts were observed for the cyclopentadienyl carbon atoms (δ 84.8 as compared to 81.5 ppm). Nitrile carbon atom of the 4-cyanopyridine (δ 117 ppm) shifted to δ 120 ppm in the complex. This downfield shift indicates deshielding of the carbon nuclei on coordination to the metal centres. This is also accompanied with an upfield shift of pyridine ring carbon atoms (δ 145–140 ppm) relative to the free ligand. The shielding of all the carbon atoms is not unexpected because of the effects of the factors like polarisation of N–C bond due to σ-bonding at the pyridine nitrogen, metal centered anisotropic diamagnetic currents and increased electron density due to π-bonding. The η⁵-C₅H₅ carbons of the 1,4-dicyanobenzene complexes resonate at δ 84.56 ppm. The nitrile carbons of these complexes resonate at δ 119.9 ppm. The downfield shift (as compared to δ 117 ppm in the free ligand) may be due to the polarisation of electron density on the carbon atom of the -C≡N group towards nitrogen upon complexation of nitrogen to ruthenium resulting into deshielding of the carbon nucleus through σ-bond. The carbon atoms of the benzene ring of 1,4-dicyanobenzene undergoes deshielding due to strong electron attracting inductive effect of CN group. These resonate at about δ 122.9 ppm in the complex as compared to the value reported for the free ligand. The other carbon atoms of the benzene (*ortho* and *meta*) appear in the region characteristic for the phenyl carbon, (δ 128.0–136.0 ppm). Though it was difficult to make a definite assignment of ¹³C nmr spectrum of 1,4-dicyanobutene complexes because of the presence of a number of signals, an intense band in the region δ 81.4 ppm may be assigned to the cyclopentadienyl carbon atoms. The CH₂ carbon atom resonates at δ 47.7 ppm. The nitrile carbon atom was observed at δ 137.4–139.2 ppm. The deshielding of carbon atom in the -C≡N moiety may be due to the polarisation of electron density from C to N atom upon coordination with nitrogen. Thus the ¹³C nmr

spectral data corroborate the conclusions drawn from the ir spectral data.

^{31}P nmr spectra : The complex formation is always accompanied by a shift in the position of phosphorous resonance δ P to a new value to δ P-M³⁰⁻³². This shift is generally negative in accord with the assumption that the formation of a donor bond from phosphorous to metal results in a decrease of the electron density on the phosphorous atom. Different factors influencing the ^{31}P resonance in the complexes are : (i) temperature independent paramagnetic contribution in diamagnetic complexes, (ii) formation of a donor σ -bond from phosphorous to metal, (iii) the contribution from $d_{\pi}-p_{\pi}$ back-donation from metal to phosphorous, (iv) aromatic ring current effects of the phenyl group, (v) bond rehybridisation effects due to changes in phosphorous bond angle on complex formation and (vi) steric effects. The ^{31}P nmr spectra of the complex containing 4-CNPY, DCB and DCBT, exhibit strong bands at δ 32 and -7.5 ppm, which have been assigned to PPh_3 phosphorous atom coordinated to ruthenium and nickel atom respectively. The deshielding of phosphorous may be caused by less donation of electrons from metal to phosphorous through back-bonding. This observation suggests that the degree of $d_{\pi}-p_{\pi}$ back-bonding is influencing the chemical shift of P atom. In these cases the PPh_3 phosphorous attached to Ni is affected by the strong σ -donor σ -bond, from P to Ni resulting in a decrease in the shielding. In this case any contribution from $d_{\pi}-p_{\pi}$ back-donation is very small. In these complexes the steric effect and bond rehybridisation effects may also play a vital role in the chemical shift of phosphorous atoms.

Electronic spectra : The low-spin d^8 and d^6 configurations of Ni^{II} and Ru^{II} in the trinuclear complexes provide filled orbitals suitable for interaction with low lying unoccupied orbitals of the ligands (4-cyanopyridine, 1,4-dicyanobenzene and 1,4-*trans*-dicyano-2-butene). Thus a metal-to-ligand charge transfer transition ($t_{2g}-\pi^*$) is expected. The energy of these transitions should vary with the ligand. The presence of a nitrile group in the ligand must cause a red-shift in the metal-to-ligand charge transfer maxima. Positions of the λ_{max}

and their assignments are given in Table 1. The electronic spectra of the complexes of 4-cyanopyridine, 1,4-dicyanobenzene, 1,4-dicyanobutene and 1,4-dicyanopiperazine exhibit broadbands of medium intensity in the region 345–376 nm and another band at 230–301 nm. These bands are found to show negative solvatochromic effect, suggesting no change in the dipole moment of the molecules. The bands at 345–376 nm have been assigned to metal-to-ligand charge transfer [Ni^{II} or Ru^{II} - Ru^{II}] of the ligands. The bands at 230–301 nm have been assigned to intra-ligand charge transfer bands (π^* -orbitals of the ligand). No band could be observed in the visible region.

Based on the above results following tentative structure has been proposed to the reaction products :

Experimental

All the chemicals (AnalaR) were used as such. Solvents were dried prior to use. Complexes $[\text{NiCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$, $[\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{E}_2)\text{Cl}]\{\text{E}_2 = (\text{PPh}_3)_2, (\text{AsPh}_3)_2, (\text{SbPh}_3)_2 \text{ and } \text{dppm}\}$ were prepared and purified by the reported procedures¹³⁻²⁰. Elemental analyses and spectral data of the complexes were obtained as described elsewhere¹⁶. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded with a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer and ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P nmr spectra with a JEOL, FT 90 Q spectrometer.

Reaction procedure : A typical reaction was carried out as follows. To a suspension of $[\text{Ni}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{L}_2]^{2+}$ (1 mmol) {where L = CNPy, DCB, PPz and DCBT} in benzene (30 ml), $[\text{Ru}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{-ClE}_2]$ {where $\text{E}_2 = (\text{PPh}_3)_2, (\text{AsPh}_3)_2, (\text{SbPh}_3)_2, \text{dppm}$ } (2 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for ~5 h. Colour of the solution generally changed to light brown. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and

evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The contents were extracted with benzene (~15 ml). After adding suitable anion (BF₄⁻, BPh₄⁻, PF₆⁻, ClO₄⁻) dissolved in methanol (25 ml) to the benzene extract, it was left for slow crystallisation. After a few hours light yellow to orange microcrystals separated out, which were centrifuged, washed with methanol (thrice) and diethyl ether (twice), and then dried under reduced pressure.

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